

Branding Strategies: A Chronological Review

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Abstract

Relying on existing literature, this paper reviews the literary, research, theoretical and practical conception, evolution and development of the field of brand management. Specifically it examines literature from 1985 to 2010, using a systems approach and methodology aimed at isolating the different research areas; the assumptions and theories they were built on; as well as relevant managerial implications. The review discovers two distinct paradigms; three time periods and seven research areas or approaches. The approaches are reviewed and discussed in details due to the important conceptual and pioneering role they played in the historic development of brand management research.

Keywords: branding, brand management, marketing, brand icons, brand evolution, product

Introduction

Branding has never been more popular than now. Large corporations and small businesses alike collectively spend billions annually in the planning and implementation of branding activities; and as such there has been an exponential surge in the research and publication of new findings and the development of frameworks as researchers frequently and relentlessly attempt to uncover the secret or golden rule to effective and successful branding processes. From the middle of the 80s till date, both researchers and practitioners have in their separate but interconnected domains, examined and explored the nature, scope and potentialities of brands thus giving birth to a plethora of ideological, theoretical and conceptual frameworks.

From a managerial perspective, this has translated into the availability of a vast array of perspectives upon which brand conceptualization, development and management could be based. The existence of this wide array of distinct perspectives thus presents the need for a periodic review of existing literature to obtain a clear and updated overview of the field of branding from time to time. However, it is obvious that an attempt to completely provide a general overview of the field of brand management will be a very daunting and practically overwhelming process due to the aforementioned. Nevertheless, relying on existing literature and especially aided by specific quality literature materials, I attempt to achieve this feat by this review article.

This paper proceeds with a presentation of a brief definition of key constructs; the introduction of the two paradigms uncovered during the process; the presentation of the three time periods and the rationality behind their categorization; the presentation of a brief, concise yet highly

informative explanation of the seven approaches, research areas or schools of thought uncovered during the review process.

Branding

Depending on the perspective from which it is viewed, the term branding has acquired a lot of different definitions over the years. However, Kotler, (2000, p. 404) documents that the most widely accepted definition is the 1960 classic definition proffered by the American Marketing Association (AMA) which linked brands to the identity of a product as well as its differentiation from its competitors by the use of clearly distinguishable visual signs and symbols (Walley, Cunstance, Taylor, Lindgreen and Hingley, 2007, p. 2) In more explicit terms, Heding, Knudtzen&Bjerre (2009, p.9) quoted the AMA as defining branding to be:

“A name, term, sign, symbol, or design; or a combination of them which is intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or a group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of competitors”

Walley et al.,(2007, p.2) however notes that in reality, a brand is not just the sum total of a name. They cite Kotler, (2000) as implying that a brand represents the promise made by a business to consistently provide its customers with certain defined set or sets of product features, benefits and services. Therefore, the fundamental objective of branding is the creation and development of a deep group of positive points which will enable customers hold favorable associations of the brand in their minds (Walley et al., 2007 p. 2). Heding et al.(2009 p. 13) went further to explain that such perceptions of the brand by the consumers is known as **brand image** and it sequentially consists of the perception, cognition and attitudes of consumers about the brand in question.

Aaker, (1991,1996) stated that another key construct in the field of brand management is the message about the brand which the business wishes to communicate to its consumers (Walley et al., 2007, p.2). This message which he referred to as **brand identity** (Aaker,1991,1996); is documented by Kapferer, (1998) to be conveyed to the consumers through a combination of the product, its unique brand name, the various symbols and distinct logos which represent it, as well as its advertising presence and the reputation of the brand creator (Walley et al. 2007, p. 2). Other key constructs pertaining to branding are practically inexhaustible and are conceived at various points throughout branding literature. For want of space however, I present a list of the most important ones as gleaned from literature examined. They include: brand loyalty, brand personality, brand genealogy, brand icons, brand extensions, brand portfolios, brand equity, brand culture, brand essence, brand audits, brand architecture, brand strategy, brand stretch, brand positioning, brand revitalization (Heding et al., 2009 p.11,12,13,14& 15) and brand awareness (Walley et al., 2007 p. 2).

The two Paradigms

The concepts of paradigms and paradigm shifts were well researched by Thomas Kuhn in his well-known work the philosophy of science (as cited by Heding et al., 2009). However the authors note that the term brand paradigm is often used at random in the field of brand management. The existence and development of patterns or paradigms throughout the history of branding research can be traced back to around 1985 when the first serious research into branding activities began in earnest (Heding et al., 2009 p. 21)

The authors after studying over 300 research articles on brand management research between 1985 and 2006, noted the existence of two distinct patterns or paradigms: the positivistic paradigm and the constructivist or interpretive paradigm (Heding et al., 2009 p. 21). The works of Abimbola, (2009) and Wilson and Liu, (2010) also confirm the persistence of the constructivist paradigm up until 2010. Figure 2 below presents a diagrammatic representation of both paradigms; and below the diagram, I present a summarized overview of both paradigms as gleaned from literature.

Figure 2: The Two Paradigms of Branding Research

Diagram Source: *Self-generated*

Content Source: *Adapted from Heding et al. (2009, p.21)*

The Positivist Paradigm

The positivist pattern or paradigm of research was observed to have existed in an era when the notion of a brand was one in which it was perceived as a resource owned solely by the seller or marketer who is responsible for and possesses the sole power to create and communicate the firm's brand message to a consumer who is considered a more or less passive recipient of the pre-constructed brand message (Heding et al., 2009 P. 21). In this paradigm, brand equity which is known to define the value of the brand; is generally believed to be created by the seller or marketer and the brand in itself as documented by Hanby, (1999 p.12) is perceived as a lifeless

artifact which can be manipulated by its owners to create a position-able and segment-able image.

The Constructivist Paradigm

On the other hand, the constructivist or interpretive paradigm which developed over the course of the 1990s; is one in which researchers and practitioners alike perceived the brand and thus brand equity unlike the positivistic paradigm; to be a living entity and process formed through the active engagement and interaction between the receptive seller or marketer and an active consumer (Hanby 1999, p.10; Heding et al., 2009 p. 21).

The Three Time Periods

Heding et al. (2009) discovered three distinct time periods in their research work; which individually embodied a chronologic concentration of similar if not homogenous research focuses literature-wise. These three time periods and their research focuses as can be seen in figure 3 below, include the periods 1985-1992; 1993-1999 and 2000-2010 as well as their research focuses- Company or sender focus; Human or receiver focus and Cultural or context focus respectively (Heding et al., 2009 p.22,23,24 and Wilson & Liu, 2010).

Figure 3: The Three Time Periods

Diagram Source: *Self-generated*

Content Source: *Adapted from Heding et al. (2009, p.21); Wilson & Liu, (2010)*

The First Time Period: 1985-1992 (Company or Sender Focus)

A review of the existing branding research literature within this period revealed that research focused mainly on the firm or company as the sender of brand message. The most common research methodology observed was the quantitative analytical method and empirical data was observed to stem primarily from either supermarket scanner systems or laboratory experimentations.

This first time period gave birth to the first two observed schools of thought or approaches in the history of brand management research: the **economic approach** and the **identity approach** (Heding et al., 2009 p.22). Both approaches and others will be explained further in the seven approach section of this article.

The Second Time Period: 1993-1999 (Human or Receiver Focus)

The attention of research literature, shifted remarkably from the company or sender focus to a more humanistic and receiver-based focus around 1993. Heding et al. (2009 p. 23) noted that this time period witnessed the application of various streams of human psychology knowledge into brand research leading to ground breaking and new research which examined the human perspectives to branding by closely investigating consumers and observing the various human brand perspectives that emerges from this new research findings. The authors also note that research methodology softened a bit during this era as researchers were observed to have used a combination of quantitative, qualitative and mixed research methods to uncover the exchange and interactions between brands and consumers (Heding et al., 2009). From this era, the authors observed the emergence of three distinct branding schools of thoughts or approaches: the **consumer-based approach**, the **personality approach** and the **relational approach**. The last approach is documented as the first branding approach entirely based on a qualitative research study (Heding et al. p, 23).

The Third Time Period: 2000-2010 (Culture or Context Focus)

Within this time period, it was observed that a duo of environmental changes and changes in academic discussions affected the way humans consumed the various brands available at the time (Heding et al. p. 24). The environmental changes mentioned above implies the need and actual development of new theoretical frameworks, due to the unexpected and practically unexplainable occurrences in the field of branding which already existing theories from previous research could not explain. Such occurrences stemmed from global technological and cultural changes which gave rise to such phenomenon as internet-based brand communities, autonomous customers, anti-brand movements and brand icons among a host of others (Heding et al. p.25). The authors note that research methodology within this era combined interdisciplinary knowledge from such fields as anthropological consumption studies, socio-cultural influences as well as consumer empowerment. As such, this time period produced the last two schools of thought or approaches observed from existing literature: the **community approach** and the **cultural approach**.

A concise, systematic and chronologic explanation of the seven approaches will now be presented in the ensuing section as gleaned from literature.

The Seven Approaches

The seven brand approaches are discoveries from the work of Heding et al. (2009) resulting from the analysis of over 300 research articles spanning a period of over twenty years. These approaches are more or less chronologic schools of thought which dominated the branding research environment at the different time periods discussed earlier. They embody a reflection of the global understanding of the nature of brands, the consumer perspectives at the time and the methodologies associated with the scientific examination of the predominant research at the time. I present these seven approaches in the chronological order which the authors believe they occurred in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: The Seven Approaches

Diagram Source: *Self-generated*

Content Source: *Adapted from Heding et al. (2009, p.21); Wilson & Liu, (2010)*

The ensuing sections of this research article will seek to shed more light on each of these seven approaches in a fashion which presents information about their general description, the **assumptions**, **theories**, research **methodologies** and **data** collection processes, as well as the **managerial implications** of each approach.

1. The Economic Approach (*sees the brand as part of the traditional marketing mix*)

This is the first noticeable school of thought gleaned from branding research and since brand management is believed to be an off shoot of marketing management, it is only natural that literature observed at this conceptual stage, based their examination and understanding of

branding activities on the traditional marketing mix theory which has its roots in the Four Ps of marketing. Heding et al. (2009, p.30) reveals that the first managerial practices of brand management were the product management activities of Procter & Gamble in the 1930s. It is in trying to understand the brand management activities of this fast growing consumer goods manufacturer at the time that the economic approach was more or less conceived. This approach was mainly influenced by the works of Borden, (1964) whose factor theory postulation laid the theoretical framework for the development of the Four Ps of marketing by McCarthy, (1964).

Brand management fully adopted the Four Ps concept during the mid and late 1980s and as such most research literature characterizing the economic approach era, were directed at exploring and seeking to understand how different factors of the marketing mix affects the consumers brand choice (Heding et al. 2009).

Assumptions of the Economic Approach

The assumptions of the economic approach as can be gleaned from the above discussion is based on the fundamentals of neoclassical microeconomic theories which is based on the idea that market forces are responsible for allocating and distributing scarce resources through the principle of the ‘invisible hand’ as well as through classical marketing theory (Heding et al., 2009). Literature examined within this approach revealed that the consumer is assumed to make brand choice decisions in a rational manner focusing on products which maximize utility. Thus brand managers believed that the consumer will only choose a brand which delivers the best utility compared to its price; over and above other brands offering anything different. Since the brand manager is solely responsible for the development of brand messages and how it is communicated; this approach assumes that brand communication thus aims at ensuring that consumers are aware of the fine utility-based qualities of the brand and its product at the right place and time, and the communication process is a linear one direct from the brand to the consumer (Heding et al., 2009).

Theoretical Foundations of the Economic Approach

According to Heding et al., (2009); theoretical foundations of the economic approach or school of thought in brand management literature, is made up of two major supporting theoretical themes and one core theme. The supporting theoretical themes are the marketing mix concept and the transaction cost theory. The later theory is one which uses the principles of the ‘invisible hand’ and the ‘economic man’ to explain difficulties which may hinder the effective transaction between the brand and the consumer. The transaction theory is also one which believes that the economic transaction or exchange between the consumer and the brand are very isolated events consisting solely of the exchange of money and goods. Thus the underlying idea is for the brand manager to do everything in his power to achieve the next transaction by strategizing to eliminate any impediments that may jeopardize the success of the transaction. Heding et al. (2009) notes that this is where the Four Ps concept comes in. It is gleaned from literature that these barriers and impediments can be eliminated in the economic approach, by the application of the right marketing mix (the Four Ps) which ensures that the right products are provided to the consumers at the right price, place and through the use of effective promotional methods all with the aim of ensuring that the consumers are aware of the product and are stimulated to make a purchase.

✚ Research Methodology & Data Analysis Processes in the Economic Approach

Heding et al., (2009, p.42) revealed that an examination of literature during the economic approach era, revealed that the most predominant methodologies adopted were quantitative in nature and concentrated on trying to understand the impact of one or more elements of the marketing mix on consumer brand choice behavior. Predominantly derived from scanner panel data, the data are usually factual and statistically measurable. Analytical methods also rely on the strength of regression and similar mathematic models which help uncover the effect of changing one variable in the marketing mix and its resultant impact on consumer brand choice behavior. Validity of research findings within this approach was also noticed to rely heavily on the ability to replicate the obtained results, since this serves as confirmation and solidifies the brand managers decision making process (Heding et al. 2009).

✚ Managerial Implications and Short Comings of the Economic Approach

An examination of literature reveals that the various tools of the economic approach is immensely valuable in the planning and implementation phases of marketing and brand management in the short term. However, more recent literature have questioned the strategic value and potentials of the use of the marketing mix in building successful brands both short term and long term. Thus it is generally accepted that the economic approach is still a suitable tool for planning and execution in the field of brand management, but this alone is not enough for the creation or building of a very successful brand in modern times hence, the need for newer approaches which consider how and why modern consumers consume brands. Heding et al. (2009) noted that this need logically gave birth to the advent of the next approach: the identity approach.

2. The Identity Approach (*Sees the brand as having links to corporate identity*)

Although the economic approach was observed to have laid down the foundations for brand management as an independent scientific discipline, literature review by Heding et al. (2009) revealed the existence of one more approach within the first time period. This approach which is observed as the second oldest, is the identity approach. Despite its age, it is a school of thought which is still relevant today with some modifications of course especially in the European brand research context.

✚ Assumptions of the Identity Approach

The general thinking of the identity approach as gleaned from literature is built on the assumption that in order to create brand value, a strong and coherent brand identity is absolutely necessary. Thus in order to create one coherent identity which meets the expectations of all stakeholders, the brand must concentrate on answering the vital question ‘who are we?’ as an organization. A shift from focusing on the product-level activities to corporate level branding activities is noticed in this approach as managers focus more on how organizational behavior affects identity, image and reputation instead of focusing solely on the visual attributes of the product alone. In this approach the previous initial assumption and perception of the consumer as a passive recipient of identity messages also changed as managers discovered that identity cannot be effectively communicated to the consumers in a linear fashion, but by interactive negotiation among all stakeholders involved.

✚ Theoretical Foundations of the Identity Approach

The theoretical foundations behind the core concept of brand identity, was discovered to include four distinct supporting theoretical themes and two key frameworks for the alignment of these supporting themes (Heding et al., 2009, p.64) Of the four themes discovered, two of them: Corporate Identity and Organizational identity theories pertain to the internal aspects of the branding process; while image and reputation are two supporting thematic theories which cater to the external aspects. Each of these four supporting themes as gleaned from literature, are believed to be important in the construction of brand identity.

However, for a coherent brand identity to be created, these four supporting themes have to be aligned together, and research revealed the existence of two distinct frameworks dedicated to this purpose. These two frameworks are the corporate brand toolkit and the AC2ID framework (Hatch and Schultz 2001, p. 131). While one takes care of the organizational culture and image; the other takes care of the actual conceived and communicated desired identity (Heding et al., 2009 p.64). The most influential literature which contributed to the identity approach is the work of Hatch and Schultz, (1997) titled *Relationship between organizational culture, identity and image*. (Heding et al., 2009).

✚ Research Methodology & Data Analysis Processes in the Identity Approach

A review of existing literature by Heding et al. (2009 p. 70) revealed that literature on the identity approach usually adopted a mix of research methodologies which actually depended on which of the four supporting themes was under examination or study. Studies which examined corporate identity data, usually applied a heuristic methodology; those which studied organizational identity often applied methodologies with firm foundations in anthropology and cultural studies. For image and reputation, a mixture of qualitative and quantitative methodologies drawn from cognitive and social psychology, were observed to be applied due to their suitability.

✚ Managerial Implications of the Identity Approach

In the brand identity approach, the most important job of the brand manager is to ensure that consumers and stakeholders alike experience a very strong and coherent brand identity in all of their contacts with it. Thus the need to align all of its identity components. As mentioned at the beginning, while this approach is documented by Heding et al. (2009) as the second approach in the history of brand management research; it nevertheless is still relevant today, but the need for subsequent approaches is documented to have arisen out of a need to better understand consumer behavior both in brand choice and purchase quantity.

3. The Consumer-based Approach (*sees the brand as linked to consumer associations*)

Kevin Lane Keller founded an entirely new approach to brand management in 1993 through his research work *Conceptualizing, Measuring and Managing Customer-based brand Equity*. (Heding et al., 2009 p. 24) In this approach, the brand is **assumed** first, to be a cognitive construal in the mind of consumers and secondly, that the minds of consumers hold strong, unique and favorable associations for a strong brand. It also assumes that although the brand resides in the mind of the consumer, the marketer is still able to control in a linear fashion, brand value creation. Three distinct **theories** form the building blocks of this approach. These are the cognitive consumer perspective, the information-processing theory of consumer choice and the

theory of customer based equity. Also three major **research methods** were observed to be common in most literature based on this approach. These are the Input-output methodologies which help in understanding how customer decisions change when stimuli are changes; Process –tracing methods which help analyze the process of brand choice among consumers and methods for measuring consumer-based brand equity (Heding et al. 2009).

4. The Personality Approach (*Sees the brand as a resembling a human character*)

When Aaker (1997) published his research study into brand personality, it was obvious that a new approach to brand management had been born. His study showed that consumers had the tendency to view and attribute human like qualities to brands. In this approach the human-brand perspective and the symbol- consuming consumer were the main focus. The approach **assumed** that personality traits are important drivers of the emotional bonding between a brand and its consumer. Drawing from **theory** from psychology about the categorization of human personality and theories of consumer-brand relationships, literature within this approach were known to apply three supporting themes: personality, consumer self and brand-self congruence as the guiding theoretical frameworks in studying brand personalities(Heding et al. 2009) An examination of existing literature revealed the use of scaling techniques and other relevant mix of quantitative and qualitative **research methods** aimed at uncovering brand personality in the data collection and analysis processes. The **managerial implication** of this approach is the ability of brand managers to create and manage brand personality by using both direct and indirect sources.

5. The Relational Approach (*Sees the brand as a viable relationship partner*)

This approach was made popular when *Consumers and their brands: developing relationship theory in consumer research* by Susan Fournier was first published in the *Journal of Consumer Research* (March 1998) (Heding et al. p.152). Building on the human brand metaphor of the identity approach; this approach introduced the brand as a viable relationship partner. This approach indicated a significant paradigm shift from the positivistic paradigm to one of a more interpretive stance. It **assumed** that the consumer is an existential being and not a passive one as earlier approaches assumed. It also assumed that brands were dyadic in nature capable of having a relationship with the consumer. A review of literature reveals that **theories** of animism, theories of human relationships and theories of brand relationships, shaped literature under this approach. The most commonly observed **research methodologies** adopted were in-depth interviews and life story methods of data collection and analyses. Also, an examination of literature revealed that this approach had implications both for the academia as well as for managers. The **academic implications** of this approach was the introduction of a dyadic brand perspective to brand management research signaling an important paradigm change; while its **managerial implications** was making brand managers aware that brands had to act as true friends if they were to create a bond in the minds of consumers (Heding et al. 2009).

6. The Community Approach (*Sees the brand as a focal point of social interaction*)

This approach is based on the observation that consumers form communities around brands thus making the brand a focal point of social interaction among enthusiastic users of a particular brand (Heding et al. 2009, p. 182). The article which influenced and popularized this approach was the article titled Brand community by Muniz and O’Guinn,(2001). This approach is based on two assumptions: a triadic brand relationship, and the perception of the brand as a social brand. The latter is a new concept added to the field of brand management by this approach. The

community theory, theories of subcultures and of consumption and the brand community theory are all theoretical frameworks which shaped literature based on this approach (Heding et al. 2009). A review of literature also showed that Ethnographic and Netographic methods are some of the most prominent research methods used in studies in this approach and the managerial implications that can be gleaned from literature under this approach sees the brand manager or marketer as an observer and facilitator of the brand building process (Heding et al. 2009).

7. The Cultural Approach (*Sees the brand as a part of the broader cultural artifact*)

The authors reveal that just like the community approach, the cultural approach emanated somewhere around the millennium, but was made more prominent and popular with the work of Holt, (2002) titled: ‘Why do brands cause trouble? A dialectic theory of consumer culture and branding’. In this approach, the brand is **assumed** to be a cultural artifact giving rise to both a very strong anti-branding discourse as well as a now prominent theory on how to build an iconic brand. In summary this approach introduced the cultural brand perspective to brand management literature. **Theories** which form the building blocks of this approach, includes the theory of cultural branding motivated by Holt’s (2002) research work; the No Logo movement and its resistance to branding and the citizen-assist brand prospect (Heding et al. 2009) The authors note that this approach borrows a lot from the scientific tradition of cultural studies and makes use of a wide variety of qualitative **methods**, most prominent of which is the application of macro-level analytical methods to micro-level data. The **managerial implications** of this approach are the view that the management of an iconic brand requires the ability to think and act like a cultural activist and also a careful consideration of corporate social responsibility (Heding et al. 2009). The table below presents a summary of the findings from the literature review on brand management.

Two Paradigms	Three Periods of Time	Research Literature Focus	Seven Brand Research Approaches or Directions
Positivistic	1985-1992	Company or Sender Focus	Economic Approach
			Identity Approach
Constructivist	1993-1999	Human or Receiver Focus	Consumer-based Approach
			Personality Approach
			Relational Approach
	2000-2010	Cultural or Context Focus	Community Approach
			Cultural Approach

Figure 5: The Review Summary

Diagram Source: *Self-generated*

Content Source: *Adapted from Heding et al. (2009, p.21); Wilson & Liu,(2010)*

Conclusion

In studying the brand research trends over the time periods under review, it was clear to see (as cited in Heding et al., 2009) the two paradigms which research literature assumed as well as the seven different brand management approaches identified between 1985 and 2010. These approaches include the economic approach, the identity approach, the consumer-based approach, the personality approach, the relational approach, the community approach, and the cultural approach. All of these approaches point to the fact that the first period of time was dominated by the sending end of brand communications while the second period of time focused on the receiving and finally the third time period focused on addressing the contextual and cultural influences on the brand; as well as the global understanding of brand management (Heding et al., 2009) It was also noted that a major paradigm shift occurred at the birth of the relational approach in 1998 and this shift brought with it an important shift away from a more quantitative research methods era to more qualitative methods and also the realization and acceptance by brand managers that the customers own the brand as well as the acceptance of the presence of other previously unacknowledged forces in the consumer's culture (Heding et al. 2009).

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